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Human Resource Audit and Engagement of Employees in SMES in Yaounde, Cameroon

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Abstract

The main objective is to examine the impact of Human Resource Audit on employee engagement in SMEs in Yaounde. Primary data was collected with the use of closed ended questionnaires administered to 113 participants, employees of 36 selected SMEs in Yaoundé VI sub-division through a blend of simple random and convenience sampling methods. Collected data was analysed using different statistical and econometric tools like correlation and multiple regression analysis, to understand the relationship between the variables. Major findings of the research reveal that there is strong positive relation between Human Resource Audit and Employee engagement using recruitment, training and remuneration audit as predictors and that these variables are valid predictors. The results gotten from the regression analysis indicate that approximately 91% of the changes on employee engagement are accounted for by human resource audit. Hence, the study recommended that, managers should pay attention to the implementation of HR practices and regularly verify if they are compliant with rules, regulations and best practices in order to secure high levels of commitment from employees towards fostering organizational growth and sustainability.

Keywords: Employee Engagement, Human Resource Audit, Recruitment Audit, Remuneration Audit, Training Audit, Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises.

1. Introduction

In a world characterized by intense competition and increase in the demands and wants of all the stakeholders, businesses have been struggling to achieve and maintain a competitive edge. Nevertheless, human capital in the business has been identified as a key source for attainment of sustained competitive edge Rabiou et al. (2019). To respond

to the demands of human capital as a source of competitive edge, organizations have developed and utilized new human capital management approaches and procedures to achieve their objectives. The present business environment is changing rapidly due to phenomena such as globalization, rapid environmental change, changing customer and investor demands, and competition to provide innovative products and services. To compete successfully in the environment, firms need to constantly improve their competitiveness by reducing costs, enhancing quality, and differentiating their products and services. The key to sustaining enviable competitiveness is the productivity of the workers. People are the most valuable resources of firms. Apart from the people, all the assets of an organization are passive resources which require human application to generate value (Fitzenz, 2000). Thus, having the right human resources (personnel) at the right place and at the right time is of utmost importance to the survival and success of any firm. Pfeiffer (2020) argued that human capital has long been held to be a critical resource in most firms.

HR audit is a comprehensive evaluation of the current HR systems and strategies, structure and competencies, culture, and impact in the context of the short and long-term business plans of a company (Usha, 2015). Olalla and Castillo (2002) revealed that HR auditing performs two basic functions. Firstly, it manages information systems whose feedback provides information about the situation in order to facilitate the development of managing processes or the development of human resource. Secondly, it is a way of controlling and evaluating the policies being applied, as well as the established processes. Thus, organizations must regularly update their human resources to survive the competition in this changing employment world (Jha, 2013). The human resource audit supports an organization to review and critically analyse the effective performance of employees and human resource functions (Minhajul, 2015). Despite the huge investments by some companies into human resource, there is a wide feeling that human resource has not lived to its expectations of either the top management or the line managers (Usha, 2015). Other challenges associated with human resource include noncompliance with employment laws, inadequate compensations and benefit plan design, not maintaining appropriate levels and poor recording (Kelli, 2008). Organizations which are discarding modern professional methods in reference to the personnel function, are unable to recruit and motivate the best specialists, or gain a reputation for being successful employers and credible partners. Unless organizations take concrete steps to understand and act on what drives employees to stay or go, the human resources bleeding will go straight to the bottom line (Gupta, 2021). In order to have a better understanding of human resource audit, it is necessary to trace out the evolution of Human Resource Management through time and have an overview of the different functions under the its area of application.

A recruitment audit is an in-depth review and analysis of a company's recruitment processes, strategies, and outcomes. It's like a health check for your hiring practices, ensuring that every part of the process from sourcing candidates to onboarding is

functioning at its best. At its core, a recruitment audit involves scrutinizing the effectiveness and efficiency of your hiring practices. It's about taking a closer look at how you attract, select, and hire talent, and assessing whether these processes align with your organization's goals and values. The purpose of conducting a recruitment audit goes beyond simply finding flaws. It's about optimizing recruitment efforts to ensure best talents are attracted, enhancing the candidate experience, and maintaining compliance with legal standards (Mia Fischer, 2019).

Effective recruitment practices contribute to higher employee satisfaction and lower turnover rates. Retaining skilled employees helps maintain continuity and reduces the costs associated with high turnover, positively impacting overall performance. The audit ensures that recruitment practices comply with legal and ethical standards. Avoiding legal issues and penalties helps protect the enterprise's reputation and financial standing, contributing to stable performance.

Goldstein and Ford (2002) argue that training audits are crucial for ensuring that training programs are aligned with organizational needs and objectives. They suggest that effective training audits help identify gaps between current performance and desired outcomes, thus enabling organizations to make data-driven decisions about training investments. By assessing the relevance and impact of training programs, a well-conducted training audit can lead to improved organizational performance by ensuring that employee development initiatives are closely linked to business goals. Donald Kirkpatrick and James Kirkpatrick's (2006) evaluation model provides a framework for understanding the relationship between training and enterprise performance. Their four-level model Reaction, Learning, Behaviour, and Results helps organizations assess the effectiveness of training programs. By evaluating these levels, organizations can determine how well training impacts employee performance and, subsequently, overall business results. Training audits using this model can reveal whether training programs are achieving desired outcomes and contributing positively to enterprise performance.

Gerhart and Rynes (2003) examine remuneration through the lens of compensation theory and empirical evidence. They highlight how compensation systems can be used to drive employee performance and align individual goals with organizational objectives. Their analysis includes the impact of different compensation structures on employee motivation, job satisfaction, and performance, as well as the strategic implications of compensation decisions. Following Milkovich and Newman (2008), he provides a comprehensive analysis of compensation systems. They discuss remuneration as a strategic tool that organizations use to attract, motivate, and retain employees. Their approach emphasizes the importance of aligning compensation strategies with organizational goals and competitive market conditions. They also explore different components of remuneration, including base pay, variable pay, benefits, and non-monetary rewards, and how these elements contribute to overall compensation packages.

Milkovich and Newman describe a remuneration audit as a comprehensive review of an organization's compensation policies, practices, and procedures.

According to Michael Armstrong (2006), a legal compliance audit is an evaluative process that reviews an organization's HR and policies to verify they are in line with relevant employment laws and regulations. This audit helps in identifying any deviations from legal requirements and implementing corrective measures. Again, Milkovich and Newman (2008) emphasize the importance of legal compliance in management. They highlight that Human resource management must comply with various laws and regulations, including those related to minimum wage, and non-discrimination. They advocate for regular audits to ensure that HR practices adhere to legal requirements and to address any compliance issues promptly.

Employee engagement matters. Companies with a highly engaged workforce have a distinct advantage. They tend to have less turnover, more productivity, and higher profits. However, according to a Gallup employee engagement poll, only 15% of the global workforce (15%) can be classified as "engaged." The need for companies to invest in employee engagement is apparent. In order to create the right engagement strategies for teams, managers need to understand how employee engagement has evolved over the years (Biyani, 2024). Historically, employee engagement was often viewed as a *Human Resources* initiative. However, over time, there has been a significant shift. Today, employee engagement is seen as a comprehensive, organization-wide strategy. It encompasses leadership styles, organizational culture, and even day-to-day management practices. Employee engagement has become more people centric, which organizations view as a strategy for attracting top talents. Modern trends indicate more flexible working conditions, hybrid working models, flexible benefits, learning and development opportunities, DEI initiatives as well as feedback culture (Grace, 2024).

In the 2000s, companies like Campbell's Soup started to realize the importance of employee engagement. During this time, companies noticed a sharp decrease in their retention rates. This massive drop was attributed to the shift towards a service economy, which encouraged flexibility. Increased market competition was another factor that pushed companies to take their turnover rates more seriously. As a result, companies were incentivized to devote time and energy to ensure that their employees' were actively participating in company activities. More importantly, companies wanted to ensure that their employees' attitudes toward the workplace were positive. Concerned with business metrics such as absenteeism, sales, and customer service, companies continued to prioritize employee engagement and invested resources into improving it. There has also been a shift in who is responsible for overseeing employee engagement. What was once a human resource responsibility, now other departments, managers, and those in leadership positions need to play a part, too. Furthermore, they need to cultivate

employee engagement and consider how to engage leaders in employee engagement, increase remote employee engagement, and explore new employee engagement ideas (Biyani, 2024).

The first step of corporate growth is the understanding of the company's pitfalls. It is important to know the weak points to advance; therefore, it is essential to conduct a performance review to learn about the weak links in an organization. In this regard, audits are an efficient way of doing so. They are an in-depth study of the business processes to understand its positives and negatives. It gives a fair idea of what needs to change. One such important audit in a company, among many others, is the HR Audit. In ascertaining these, an HR Audit looks into the various fronts of human resource personnel's work. Some of these are: Legal compliance audit, Hiring Procedure audit, Employee Onboarding audit, Compensation and Remuneration audit, Benefits Package audit, Performance Review audit, Termination of Tenure, Exit Interview (Jyoti Prakash Barman, 2024). Sherer and Kent (1983) state that Multiple Group of companies' objective of carrying out human resource audit is to get more information about the rewarding system, training, recruitment and selection and recommend policies for improving its performance. According to Lev and Schwartz (2017), HR audit practices helps to uncover areas of liability exposure, cost and opportunity on three levels: the audit helps focus on what needs to be known to generate even better human resource system results. It also helps to correct misunderstandings, oversights, mistakes and missed opportunities.

In the Cameroonian context characterized by a complicated business climate in which small and medium enterprises face problems like limited access to capital, complex procedure of enterprise creation, complex fiscal system, inability to match-up with international competition, the absence of an effective human resource audit will lead to the death of the enterprise (RGE, 2009). According to the 'Centre de Formalité et de Creation d'Entreprises (CFCE, 2014)', about 80% of SMEs created in Cameroon die before their 5th anniversary with the principal causes being limited access to capital, complex fiscal system. The success or failure of any SME is neither an abstract phenomenon nor a matter of chance. Good corporate management is a factor that determines success. Despite the government's effort to promote and develop the small and medium enterprises such as the creation of the Ministry of Small and Medium size enterprises, the creation of the Bank of Small and Medium size enterprises as a means of enhancing industrial development in Cameroon, the sector's growth has been hampered by a multitude of problems (Negou et al., 2023). In the contemporary business environment, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) face increasing pressure to optimize their operations for sustainability and growth. One critical but often underemphasized area is the management of human resources (HR). Human Resource Audits (HRAs) are systematic evaluations of an organization's HR policies, procedures, and practices, aimed

at identifying strengths and areas for improvement. While large corporations frequently invest in HRAs, SMEs often neglect this practice due to resource constraints or lack of awareness. This oversight can lead to inefficiencies, legal compliance issues, and missed opportunities for employee development and organizational growth. Despite the critical role human capital plays in the success of small and medium-sized enterprises, many SMEs do not conduct regular Human Resource Audits. This neglect can result in several issues such as legal compliance risk, operational inefficiency, missed strategic opportunities (Boxall and Purcell, 2016). From here, the central question of our research is: What is the impact of Human Resource Audit on the Engagement of workers in Cameroon SMEs?

The main objectives of this research is to investigate on the relationship between Human Resource Audit and the Engagement of employees in SMEs in Yaounde, Cameroon.

2. Literature Review

a. Theoretical review

To examine the relationship between human resource audit and the employee engagement, researchers have used diverse theories in order to have a better apprehending on the subject matter. Some of these theories include: the Human Capital Theory developed in the 1960s by the economists Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz. It pointed out that education and training were investments that could add to productivity; the Social Capital Theory developed by the Sociologists Pierre Bourdieu in the 1980-1990s. Initially, social scientists believed that social capital was morally neutral because everyone possesses it to a certain degree. However, they soon learned that a person's position within a particular group provides certain benefits that work to their advantage and hopefully benefit the community. This idea became known as social capital theory. Best fit HRM theories which are also known as universalistic theories postulates that HRM Practices are universal in the sense that they are best in any situation and that adopting them will lead to superior organizational performance. Universalistic scholars Luthans & Summers (2005) and Pfeiffer (2001) argue that there is a set of superior HRM practices which if adopted by a firm, would lead to enhanced firm performance. A crucial aspect concerning SHRM is the concepts of fit and flexibility. The degree of fit determines the human resource system's integration with organization strategy (Kumar, 2006). At last, The Resource Based Theory, the fundamentals of the Resource-Based View (RBV) of the firm can be found in the work of Penrose (1959) on the "Theory of the Growth of the Firm", which conceived the firm as an administrative organization and a collection of productive resources, both physical and human. Both material resources and human resources can provide the firm a variety of usefulness. Thus, the resource-based theory of the firm combines concepts from organizational economics and strategic management (Barney, 1991).

b. Empirical review

Regarding the concept of Human resource audit, a number of empirical studies have been conducted by researchers in different parts of the world. However, only few studies are found across Africa and Cameroon in particular. The methodologies adopted by the researchers are different and they cover different time periods in different geographical regions as well as different industries and sectors of activity. Within the framework of studies by researchers in Cameroon, very little research has been done in the area of HRA and especially within SMEs. A brief review of studies is presented below.

Vijay (2024) investigated HR Audit in selected print media organization of Madhya Pradesh in India. In order to explore the impact of human resource audit on entire HR functions, certain practices of HR such as job analysis, performance appraisal, reward management and compensation were tested. The findings of the study indicated that human resource audit of print media organization is playing a most significant role in order to effectively examination of various HR functions with respect to job analysis, performance appraisal, reward management and compensation. The research conclusions suggested that HR audit should include the purpose of audit, examination of HR compliance as well as organizational policies.

Ingrid Konomi et al. (2023) conducted a research study on human resource audit in Albania. The purpose of this research was to measure the effectiveness of human resource audit on organisational efficiency. The study explored that human resource audit is one of the most important processes of each and every organization. The relationship between the effectiveness of functions and work efficiency was positive, which means that, when the effectiveness of the functions increases, the efficiency at work is also expected to increase. This is also supported by the empirical analysis, where a distinction was made between the association of the evaluation coefficients and the level of reliability for the two factors in question. The same situation is with the management climate. A second result which was related to the importance of legal policies and procedures as a factor that determines efficiency at work, was unsatisfactory along with motivation and evaluation. It was however explored by the study that human resource audit is related with profit maximization of the company.

Devera et al. (2022) conducted a research study on impact on human resource audit in Indian SMES. The study was based on primary data which has been collected by the observation and survey method. Sample for the study was taken from the 100 peoples. The findings of the study not only explore the impact of HR audit on Indian SMES but also found the elements for the success of the organization. Furthermore in the conclusive remark it has been pointed out by the author that human resource audit in SMES helps to examine the strength of HR practices.

Fabian et al. (2017) carried out a study to examine the role of human resource audit on employee turnover at tertiary institutions in Uganda. Both purposive and simple random

sampling procedure was used and a sample of 97 participants was selected for the study and data was analysed using SPSS statistical package. The study found out that Human resource audit is not the only function responsible for the level of turnover in Uganda Colleges of Commerce and that employees who perceive to carry skills that are highly demanded are lured away by higher pays. The study recommended that the human resource department of the Ministry of Education and Sport should review their human resource policy to address the loopholes in staff compensation, recruitment and salary and Supervisors at the institutions should ensure sound supervisory practices, which promote decision-making, recognition of employees' efforts and unique skills and accomplishments.

Ambosu (2017) studied Human Resource Audit and organizational performance in the county government of Kisumu, Kenya. The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between selected HRA approaches and organizational performance in Kisumu County. The specific objectives of the study were to establish the relationship between compliance audit approach and organizational performance, to determine the relationship between productivity audit approach and organizational performance and to establish moderating effect of organizational factors on the relationship between HRA and organizational performance. The study was guided by a conceptual framework which shows the interrelationship between the variables as conceptualized by the author. The research findings revealed that organizations that regularly audit compliance with employment rules and regulation will improve in performance. He went further to recommend that County government should strengthen HRA policies in their counties, so as to improve the performance of its human resource functions. There is a need that HRA process in an organization should involve every employee and not only the managerial staff. County government need to relook at a number of key HR products and services if they want to improve their current level of performance.

Gesare *et al.* (2016) carried out a research which was guided by HR audit as a performance management initiative and its influence on service delivery in State Corporations in Kenya. Using four dimensions of HR audit; function audit, compliance audit, service audit and strategic audit, the study found that HR audit has a positive influence on service delivery among state corporations in Kenya and the researchers recommended that state corporations in Kenya adopt HR audits because they positively and significantly influence service delivery. The study however did not examine the differences in performance among the state corporations to establish whether differences in service delivery among the firms were attributed to HR audit. It equally globalised all state corporations without considering differences in their classes.

Lydia (2016) conducted a research study to explore the role of human resource audit in the organization. The purpose of the research study is to explore the role of audit to examine human resources practices in the organization. The study was based on primary data which has been obtained by using structure interview and questionnaire. The

findings of the study explore that majority of respondent agrees that the organization is developed a well-defined strategy to utilize modern HR practices to help the organization to achieve the target. Furthermore study concluded that an effective HR audit helps organization to examine and improve entire HR activities of the organization. Saleem and Akbar (2015) evaluated the role of HR audit on organizational effectiveness drawing evidence from the banking sector in Karachi-Pakistan. The study identified that banks had not adopted a professional audit system for human resource practices in line with changing market realities. The respondents revealed that focus on improving the HR functions and implementations with the alignment of compliance and legal review lead to the strong human resource audit system in banking industry, having the attractive compensation packages can also be a part of retaining the employees in organizations which shows the good implementation of HR practices in organizations, and besides the compensation packages others factors like; training and development, recruitment and selection, performance management system, career development, succession planning, employee retention also have an important aspects towards organization effectiveness. Lydia and Willy (2015) conducted a research on the effects of HR audit on the performance of secondary schools in Kenya. However, this dimension of audit does not clearly reveal if the organization is achieving its goals and objectives. Using, the variable of compliance with managerial policies, procedures and legal provision provided by the government, the results obtained were positive. The elaborate study done in conceptualizing compliance audit indicates its relevance to the organization. However, the study failed to clearly establish and draw a general conclusion on the effect of HR audit on employee performance. The study equally laid Emphasis on the employee situation and not the human resource audit itself from an organizational view point. Laboso (2015) studied Human Resource Audit practice and the performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study evidenced the practice of HR audit in banks and that they are intended to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of HR functions geared towards improving alignment between Human Resource function and corporate strategies. The results showed that the banks human resource audit entails the examination of policies, procedures, documentation, systems and practices with respect to its human resource function. The management of the banks are committed to fostering co-operative relations with the unions representing the employees and the union leaders in order to achieve the banks objectives. Finally, the study revealed that human resource audit influenced various performance indicators in the banks including employee, shareholders as well as the organization in general.

For a developing country like Cameroon striving for emergence by 2035, a rise in private sector activities is a crucial advantage to attaining this vision. Small and Medium Size Enterprises (SMEs) are acknowledged among the greatest sectors vital to economic development (Dadem et al., 2024). The advent of increasing start-ups gives rise to increased competition within the business environment as many of these small

businesses are tailored to solving similar problems in their respective sectors. Worthy of note is the fact that employees are the life blood of every organization and HR practitioners who consider this core concept as a pivotal key to organizational success search for maximum ways to keep its employees at their highest. It is therefore a question of what keeps the organization competitive; technology, employee commitment, organizational vision or HR practices, policies and procedures in themselves. Given that many of such SMEs are in similar domains, it is important for management to stay alert on the practices which keep the workforce engaged, thereby creating room for renewed efforts, creative solutions and commitment.

A number of studies relating to employee engagement within organizations and SMEs in particular have been carried out. Olga Limunga (2017) conducted a study on performance appraisal methods and job commitment. The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of appraisal on employees in selected companies and the results obtained revealed differences for different companies. The study failed to separate large companies from smaller ones. Another study conducted by Andre and Njifen (2019) on employee involvement in the administrative sector through engagement drivers revealed that that the gender, professional experience and level of education of the official, all other things being equal, positively influence their degree of attachment to the public service. Contract staffs feel less involved than other socio-professional categories (civil servants, uniformed personnel and contract managers). The study did not highlight employee involvement with reference to HR practices and also was conducted for the civil service sector. Chevalier de Dieu (2019) also did a study on organizational justice and organizational commitment of public secondary school teachers and this research was only tailored for the educational sector. Eugene (2020) made findings on the role of organizational culture on employee satisfaction in the banking sector (UBA Bank). This research revealed a positive relationship but was specific to one bank out of many.

Despite the numerous studies on employee engagement mentioned above, the aspect of Human Resource audit and employee engagement with respect to SMEs has been neglected. There is no existing literature within the Cameroonian context directly associated with HR audit and this has attracted considerable attention for the study.

The extent to which the established Human resource functions support the performance of the organisation is very important. Through the HR audits areas of weakness and strength can be identified and this prompts for adjustments for improvements where necessary. One of the most important functions of an HR measurement system, according to Becker et al. (2001), is that it provides a means to identify the discrepancies between the organizations's current and its ideal HR architecture. Such an assessment needs to focus on both cost and benefits (quality). Hence, the absence of human resource audit will have adverse consequences for the organization.

Despite the existence of literature on HR audit in other countries, none has tested the concept as a determinant of employee engagement. The reviews of studies above indicate

that there are very few studies on human resource audit practices amongst companies in Cameroon talk less of within SMEs. It is important to note that if organizations set up policies, procedures, methods and strategies for their company functioning, but do not review how well these policies and methods influence organizational outcomes, there will be difficulty in appreciating helpful methods as well identifying areas where shortcomings results from, in order to address the gaps. As a result of scarcity of studies on HRA practices within SMEs in Cameroon, this study is intended to bridge the knowledge gap by introducing HR audit practices in the organizational processes, and determining whether or not HR audits influence employee engagement within these SMEs.

3. Methodology

a. Area of study

The primary focus of this study is on the relationship and impact of human resource audit on the performance of small and medium size commercial enterprises in Yaounde. However, it is important to note that our study did not cover all the aspect and sections of human resource audit but limited to some specific variables which are to Recruitment audit, Training audit, Remuneration audit and Legal compliance audit. The research also focuses on key aspect of enterprise performance identified through the literature review and searched objectives.

Our study was based on the performance of small and medium size enterprises, precisely on small and medium size commercial enterprises in the Centre Region of Cameroon. The research was limited within some randomly selected small and medium size commercial enterprises Yaoundé, the political capital of Cameroon. Commercial enterprises are businesses that operate with the primary goal of earning profit. They engage in various economic activities such as selling goods, providing services, or both. These enterprises can range from small local businesses, like a corner store or a café, to large multinational corporation. According to law number 2015/010 of 16 July 2015 on the promotion of Small and Medium size enterprises in Cameroon; enterprises are considered as SME's no matter their domain of activity when they employ a maximum of 100 workers and when their "Chiffre D'affaire hors tax" (CAHT) does not exceed 3 billion (Negou et al., 2023).

b. Research design

The study adopted a descriptive and correlational research design whereby the researcher sought to test the relationship between the dependent and independent variables, and also describing existing phenomenon, using a quantitative research approach (deduction) which involved statistical analysis and hypothesis testing, and results were interpreted using numerical and statistical values.

c. Nature and sources of data

Primary data was collected with the use of closed ended questionnaires from 113 participants, who were employees of 36 selected SMEs within Yaoundé VI sub-division.

The study applied a blend of simple random and convenience sampling methods in selecting participants for the study. The main variables of this research include recruitment audit, training audit, remuneration audit and compliance audit that were all correlated and regressed against the Engagement of Employees in Selected SMEs in the Yaounde IV municipality within a data collection period of 4 months.

d. Model Specification

Model specification refers to the determination of which independent variables should be included in or excluded from a regression equation. The independent variable represented by X is HRA, while the dependent variable which is represented by Y is Employee Engagement. From the perceived relationship between Human Resource Audit and Employee Engagement, functional relationships were established using three key predictors; recruitment, training and remuneration audits and are presented in a Multiple Regression model as seen below:

$$Y_i = f(x)$$

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 \dots + \epsilon$$

Where;

Y = dependent variable (Employee engagement)

X = independent variable (Human Resource Audit)

Further, we can bring out the following models to see which variables are significant with employee engagement.

$$EE = f(\text{HRA})$$

$$EE_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 R A_i + \beta_2 T A_i + \beta_3 R e A_i + \epsilon_i$$

Where;

β_0 = constant (other factors different from HRA that can affect EE such as pay structure, motivation, company culture, and work environment etc.)

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = slope of regression coefficients (unknown)

RA = recruitment audit

TA = training audit

ReA = remuneration audit

ϵ = error term

4. Presentation and Discussion of Findings

a. Descriptive statistics

Our analyses are based on the established significant relationship that exist between Human resource audit and the engagement of employees in small and medium size enterprises in Yaoundé. The data were presented by using table and figures, hypotheses were tested by using regression analysis technique. The variables that were tested were Recruitment audit, Training audit and Remuneration audit against Employee Engagement.

Table 1: Summary of Demographic Information

		Statistics					
		Age bracket	Gender	Size of the enterprise	Sector of activity	Longevity in service	Level of education
N	Valid	113	113	113	113	113	113
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.19	1.49	2.15	2.47	2.11	3.92
Median		2.00	1.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	4.00
Mode		2	1	3	3	1	4
Std. Deviation		.527	.502	.793	.733	1.175	1.226
Variance		.278	.252	.629	.537	1.381	1.503
Skewness		1.301	.054	-.277	-1.000	.429	.006
Std. Error of Skewness		.227	.227	.227	.227	.227	.227
Kurtosis		2.888	-2.033	-1.355	-.424	-1.399	-.149
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.451	.451	.451	.451	.451	.451

Source: Fieldwork, (2024)

The above output provides descriptive statistics for a dataset related to the following:

Age, categorized into the data has a positive skew indicating more extreme values on the higher end. The distribution is leptokurtic, meaning it's more peaked than a normal distribution. The standard deviation is relatively low, indicating a compact distribution. The gender variable is likely coded as 1 (male) and 2 (female), given the mean and median. The distribution is almost symmetrical (skewness near 0). The standard deviation is moderate, indicating some variation.

The enterprise sizes are moderately varied (standard deviation = 0.793). The distribution is slightly negatively skewed, indicating more large enterprises. The mode (3) is greater than the mean and median, suggesting a few larger enterprises. Possible Enterprise Size Categories: Assuming sizes are coded as: 1 = Small, 2 = Medium, 3 = Large and 4 = Very Large. 42.5% Medium (median = 2), 34.5% Large (mode = 3) and 23% Small/Large/Very Large. This interpretation depends on the specific coding scheme and categories used. - Sectors are moderately varied (standard deviation = 0.733). The distribution is negatively skewed, indicating more sectors coded as 3. The mode (3) is greater than the mean, suggesting a dominant sector. Longevity in service varies moderately (standard deviation = 1.175). The distribution is positively skewed, indicating more short-term

service. The mode (1) is less than the mean and median, suggesting a few longer-term services.

Education levels are moderately varied (standard deviation = 1.226). The distribution is nearly symmetrical, indicating a balanced spread. The mode (4) aligns with the median, suggesting a dominant education level. The average education level is approximately Bachelor's degree. There's a strong presence of Bachelor's degree holders. Fewer individuals have other academic qualifications.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Descriptive Statistics									
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
TRAINING AUDIT	113	1	5	1.96	.839	1.563	.227	3.773	.451
RECRUITMENT AUDIT	113	1	5	2.35	.943	.687	.227	.363	.451
EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT	113	1	5	2.85	1.187	.320	.230	-.793	.457
REMUNERATION AUDIT	113	1	5	3.39	1.417	-.222	.227	-1.346	.451
Valid N (listwise)	113								

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Remuneration Audit scores are the highest, indicating strengths in compensation. Employee Engagement scores are above average, suggesting positive workforce sentiment. Recruitment Audit scores are moderate, indicating room for improvement. Training Audit scores are the lowest, highlighting areas for development. Training Audit scores are most consistent, Recruitment Audit scores show moderate diversity, Employee Engagement scores vary more while Remuneration Audit scores show the most variability

Training: Consistency suggests effective program implementation Recruitment: Moderate diversity may indicate varied candidate quality. Employee Engagement: Variability suggests differing workforce experiences. Remuneration: High variability may indicate inconsistent compensation practices.

Training Audit scores cluster at the lower end. Recruitment Audit scores show moderate clustering. Employee Engagement scores are relatively balanced. Remuneration Audit scores cluster at the higher end. For training, lower scores may indicate room for

improvement. Recruitment: Moderate clustering suggests varied candidate quality. Employee Engagement: Balanced scores indicate overall satisfaction. Remuneration: Higher scores suggest competitive compensation.

The standard error of skewness (SES) measures the reliability of the skewness statistic. SES values are relatively consistent across categories (~0.227-0.230). This indicates similar reliability for skewness estimates. To construct 95% confidence intervals for skewness: $\text{Skewness} \pm (1.96 \times \text{Std. Error})$. Training Audit: 1.563 ± 0.445 . Recruitment Audit: 0.687 ± 0.445 . Employee Engagement: 0.320 ± 0.451 . Remuneration Audit: -0.222 ± 0.445 Insights: Skewness estimates are reliable, given similar standard errors. Confidence intervals provide a range for expected skewness values.

Training Audit: Leptokurtic (3.773). Distribution is more peaked than normal. Recruitment Audit: Mesokurtic (0.363). Distribution resembles normal curve. Employee Engagement: Platykurtic (-0.793). Distribution is less peaked, more flat. Remuneration Audit: Platykurtic (-1.346). Distribution is even less peaked, more uniform. Training Audit scores cluster tightly around mean. Recruitment Audit scores distribute normally. Employee Engagement and Remuneration Audit scores vary widely. Training: Consistent scores suggest effective training. Recruitment: Normal distribution indicates varied candidate quality. Employee Engagement and Remuneration: Wide variability suggests diverse experiences.

b. Correlations

Relationship between Remuneration Audit, Training Audit, Recruitment Audit and Employee Engagement

Table 3: Correlations

		Correlations			
		EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT	RECRUITMEN T AUDIT	REMUNERATIO N AUDIT	TRAININ G AUDIT
EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT	Pearson Correlatio n	1	.916**	.784**	.904**
	Sig. (2- tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	113	113	113	113
RECRUITMENT AUDIT	Pearson Correlatio n	.916**	1	.855**	.841**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	113	113	113	113
REMUNERATIO N AUDIT	Pearson Correlatio n	.784**	.855**	1	.683**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	113	113	113	113
TRAINING AUDIT	Pearson Correlatio n	.904**	.841**	.683**	1
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	113	113	113	113

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

A Pearson's correlation was run to determine the relationship between Recruitment Audit, Remuneration Audit, Training Audit and Employee Engagement as indicated on the table above. The significant Pearson's correlation coefficient value of 0.916, 0.784 and 0.904 that is 91.6%, 78.4%, 90.4% respectively for the variables confirms that there appears to be a very strong positive correlation between Recruitment Audit, Training Audit and Employee Engagement while there is a strong relationship between remuneration Audit and employee engagement. Given a 0.01 significance level, the observations reveal that the calculated value for all variables computed is greater than the table value; hence the decision rule here is that we reject the null hypotheses and fail to reject the alternative.

c. Regression

Table 4: Coefficients of different variables

Model	Coefficients ^a				T	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Beta		
	B	Std. Error				
(Constant)	-.164	.101			-1.629	.106
1 RECRUITMENT	.584	.097	.456		6.044	.000
AUDIT						
TRAINING AUDIT	.117	.080	.082		1.457	.148
REMUNERATION						
AUDIT	.404	.046	.469		8.759	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

From the econometric package run using the 113 respondents of our sample size, the constant (-0.164) represents the baseline value of the dependent variable. For every unit increase in: Recruitment Audit, the dependent variable increases by 0.584. Training Audit, the dependent variable increases by 0.117. Remuneration Audit, the dependent variable increases by 0.404. Recruitment Audit has the strongest positive impact on the dependent variable. Remuneration Audit also has a significant positive effect. Training Audit's impact is relatively smaller. Lower standard errors indicate more precise estimates.

Recruitment Audit's standard error (0.097) is relatively low, indicating a reliable estimate. Remuneration Audit's standard error (0.046) is the lowest, suggesting a precise estimate. Training Audit's standard error (0.080) is moderate. Reliable estimates support confident decision-making. Prioritize Recruitment and Remuneration Audits due to their precision. Refine Training Audit processes to improve precision. Beta values measure the relative importance of each predictor. Recruitment Audit (0.456) and Remuneration Audit (0.469) have significant, positive impacts. Training Audit (0.082) has a relatively small impact. Recruitment and Remuneration Audits are equally important predictors. Training Audit's impact is negligible. Focus on Recruitment and Remuneration Audits for process improvements. Re-evaluate Training Audit's effectiveness.

Consider additional predictors to enhance model fit t-values measure the statistical significance of each predictor. P-values corresponding to t-values: Recruitment Audit ($p = 0.000$) and Remuneration Audit ($p = 0.000$) are highly significant. Training Audit ($p = 0.147$) is not statistically significant. Constant term is marginally significant ($p = 0.106$). Recruitment and Remuneration Audits strongly predict the outcome variable. Training Audit may not contribute significantly. Refine model by reconsidering Training Audit or adding new predictors. P-values < 0.05 indicate statistical significance. P-values > 0.05 indicate no statistical significance. Recruitment Audit ($p = 0.000$) and Remuneration

Audit ($p = 0.000$) are highly significant. Training Audit ($p = 0.148$) is not statistically significant. Constant term is marginally significant ($p = 0.106$). Recruitment and Remuneration Audits strongly predict the outcome variable. Training Audit may not contribute significantly. Refine model by reconsidering Training Audit or adding new predictors.

Table 5: model summary

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.952 ^a	.907	.904	.367

a. Predictors: (Constant), REMUNERATION AUDIT, TRAINING AUDIT, RECRUITMENT AUDIT

b. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

Source: *Fieldwork*, 2024

Looking at the table above, the regression result indicated R (0.952): Strong positive correlation between predictors and outcome variable. R Square (0.907): Approximately 91% of variance in outcome variable explained by predictors. Adjusted R Square (0.904): Model fit remains strong after adjusting for degrees of freedom. Std. Error of Estimate (0.367): Model predictions have moderate accuracy. The model has excellent predictive power. Recruitment Audit and Remuneration Audit significantly contribute to the model. Training Audit may require refinement.

5. Conclusions, Recommendations and Suggestion for Future Research

a. Summary of findings

The research questions which the study sought to answer were transformed and formulated as hypotheses, which were tested using regression analysis. The results computed indicate an overall favourable situation. The number of respondents used in the study indicates that 33.4% and 39.8% of respondents were gotten from Small and Medium enterprises respectively. This gives a total of 73.2% which is an acceptable representation of SMEs in the sample. Therefore, the findings can be related to SMEs.

The result obtained from the regression analysis computed indicates a strong positive correlation between sub-independent variables (predictors; recruitment, training and remuneration audits) and dependent or outcome variable (employee engagement). The coefficient of determination (R-Square) is 0.907, which indicates that approximately 91% of variance in the outcome variable is explained by the predictors, thereby giving it an excellent predictive power. The results equally reveal that the model has strong predictive and adequate statistical power and is also highly significant.

Recruitment Audit is a strong contributor to overall reliability. The computed Pearson's correlation equally revealed a very strong positive correlation with employee

engagement. The computed coefficients indicated that an increase in recruitment audit will result to a positive increase in employee engagement and it had the strongest impact. For training audit, the computed Pearson's coefficient was very strong as well as the coefficients indicated that an increase in training audit lead to improved employee engagement. Training audits, while important, however, revealed a negligible impact and so may require refinement for optimal impact. Hence, regular assessment and refining of the components related to training is required to maintain high employee engagement.

On the side of remuneration audit, the Pearson's coefficient was strong as well. An increase in remuneration audit results to a significant increase in employee engagement.

b. Recommendations

From the research findings and conclusions, for SMEs in Yaoundé to ameliorate the level of employee engagement, we suggest that they should;

Recruitment audit: As concerns audit of recruitment, the study recommends that organizations prioritize recruitment audit processes to maximize impact. Getting staff or employees who will create a long lasting impact in the organization begins from applying the right recruitment process as suits the organizational circumstances and prevailing labour market conditions. Refining recruitment processes will attract top talents, as starting right always often makes it right.

Orientation and induction processes also require improvement for more effective recruitment as it is relevant for new hires to bond and feel that they are acknowledged and welcome to be a significant part of the organization's success from the onset and moving forward. The increased use of enhanced ICT tool in recruitment is equally vital and as a means to maintain transparent communication and formal documentation.

Training audit: in the domain of training, the research suggests that managers plan and implement training programs for employees in different categories as need be, and continuously evaluate training effectiveness. Invest in training programs to enhance skills. Foster employee engagement through open communication, feedback and recognition.

Regularly evaluating and updating HR practices gives room to maximize employee commitment, as areas of improvement are identified and attended to accordingly. It is important for managers to verify which practices are bringing in the most results, which areas require improvement and strategizing as well as which particularities relate to individual employees, departments and services.

Remuneration audit: managers are encouraged to ensure equitable and fair remuneration practices and maintain competitive pay packages to attract and retain top talents which will spiral increased efforts towards supporting growth. Compensation and benefits should be objective and follow statutory regulations in order to enhance employee loyalty. Employers can equally provide opportunities for flexible pay and remunerate overtime hours put in for work.

By the implementation of HRA within SMEs, managers can identify areas for improvement in their HR practices. The principal aim is to ameliorate these conditions so that employees are more engaged to pursue organizational profitability. When employees are engaged, they are prone to being most productive and efficient, and this results in improved organizational outcomes; profitability, growth and sustainability. Hence, the motive of HRA is not just to get employees engaged and be committed or improve employee circumstances, but for this engagement to be translated to better conditions for the organization.

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